

Supplementary Materials

Supplementary Materials 1: AD2

Fig. 1. Gain of AD2 in loopback mode. Top: AWG output is 100mV; Middle: AWG output is 1V; Bottom: AWG output is 5V.

Fig. 2. Crosstalk of AD2 between channel 1 and channel 2. AWG output is 100mV, 1V and 5V. Unconnected channel is loaded with a 10k Ω resistor.

Supplementary Materials 2: Voltage Readout

Fig. 1. Gain of voltage readout channel. Gain is set between 1V/V and 5V/V via the IAs digital inputs. Output of IA is 1V. Voltage input is adjusted accordingly.

Fig. 2. Gain of voltage readout channel. Gain is set between 10V/V and 100V/V via the IAs digital inputs. Output of IA is 1V. Voltage input is adjusted accordingly.

Fig. 4. Gain of voltage readout channel. Input resistor is set between 100Ω and $100k\Omega$. Gain is set to $1V/V$. Output voltage is 1V.

Fig. 5. Gain of voltage readout channel. Output voltage is set between 100mV and 5V. Gain is set to $1V/V$.

Fig. 6. THD+N of voltage readout channel. Gain is set between 1V/V and 5V/V (top) and 10V/V to 100V/V (bottom) via the IAs digital inputs. Output of IA is 1V. Voltage input is adjusted accordingly.

Fig. 7. THD+N of voltage readout channel. Input resistor is set between 100Ω and $100k\Omega$. Gain is set to 1V/V. Output voltage is 1V.

Fig. 8. THD+N of voltage readout channel. Output voltage is set between 100mV and 5V. Gain is set to 1V/V.

Fig. 9. Crosstalk between voltage readout channels. Gain is set between 1V/V and 5V/V (top) and 10V/V to 100V/V (bottom) via the IAs digital inputs. Output of IAs is 1V. Voltage input is adjusted accordingly.

Fig. 10. Crosstalk between voltage readout channels. Input resistor is set between 100Ω and $100k\Omega$. Gain is set to $1V/V$. Output voltage is $1V$.

Fig. 8. Crosstalk between voltage readout channels. Output voltage is set between $100mV$ and $5V$. Gain is set to $1V/V$.

Bandwidth	Mismatch (1kHz)	Mismatch (10MHz)	Crosstalk (1kHz)
>10MHz ⁽¹⁾	0.06dB ⁽¹⁾	1.8dB ⁽¹⁾	-65dB ⁽¹⁾
>10MHz ⁽²⁾	0.05dB ⁽²⁾	1.6dB ⁽²⁾	-88dB ⁽²⁾
1.7MHz ⁽³⁾	0.07dB ⁽³⁾	0.75dB ⁽³⁾	-108dB ⁽³⁾
Crosstalk (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
-42dB ⁽¹⁾	-35dB ⁽¹⁾	-17dB ⁽¹⁾	1.2mV ⁽¹⁾
-42dB ⁽²⁾	-54dB ⁽²⁾	-22dB ⁽²⁾	1.2mV ⁽¹⁾
-38dB ⁽³⁾	-55dB ⁽³⁾	-22dB ⁽³⁾	1.3mV ⁽¹⁾

Table 1. Measured performances of the Voltage Readout Channels. Gain is set to 1V/V (0dB). Unused channel is loaded with a 10kΩ resistor. ⁽¹⁾ IA output signal is 100mVpp. ⁽²⁾ IA output signal is 1Vpp. ⁽³⁾ IA output signal is 5Vpp.

Bandwidth	Mismatch (1kHz)	Mismatch (10MHz)	Crosstalk (1kHz)
>10MHz ⁽¹⁾	0.08dB ⁽¹⁾	1.7dB ⁽¹⁾	-88dB ⁽¹⁾
>10MHz ⁽²⁾	0.07dB ⁽²⁾	1.6dB ⁽²⁾	-88dB ⁽²⁾
>10MHz ⁽³⁾	0.07dB ⁽³⁾	1.6dB ⁽³⁾	-88dB ⁽³⁾
Crosstalk (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
-47dB ⁽¹⁾	-54dB ⁽¹⁾	-22dB ⁽¹⁾	1.1mV ⁽¹⁾
-42dB ⁽²⁾	-54dB ⁽²⁾	-22dB ⁽²⁾	1.1mV ⁽²⁾
-42dB ⁽³⁾	-54dB ⁽³⁾	-22dB ⁽³⁾	1.2mV ⁽³⁾

Table 2. Measured performances of the Voltage Readout Channels. Output voltage is 1V. Gain is set to 1V/V (0dB). Unused channel is loaded with a 10kΩ resistor. ⁽¹⁾ IA input load is a 100Ω resistor. ⁽²⁾ IA input load is a 10kΩ resistor ⁽³⁾ IA input load is a 100kΩ resistor

Bandwidth	Mismatch (1kHz)	Mismatch (10MHz)	Crosstalk (1kHz)
>10MHz ⁽¹⁾	0.06dB ⁽¹⁾	1.7dB ⁽¹⁾	-88dB ⁽¹⁾
>10MHz ⁽²⁾	0.07dB ⁽²⁾	1.7dB ⁽²⁾	-88dB ⁽²⁾
10MHz ⁽³⁾	0.07dB ⁽³⁾	1.6dB ⁽³⁾	-88dB ⁽³⁾
7.3MHz ⁽⁴⁾	0.07dB ⁽⁴⁾	1.6dB ⁽⁴⁾	-88dB ⁽⁴⁾
8.1MHz ⁽⁵⁾	0.07dB ⁽⁵⁾	1.6dB ⁽⁵⁾	-88dB ⁽⁵⁾
5.2MHz ⁽⁶⁾	0.07dB ⁽⁶⁾	1.8dB ⁽⁶⁾	-88dB ⁽⁶⁾
2.9MHz ⁽⁷⁾	0.08dB ⁽⁷⁾	2.0dB ⁽⁷⁾	-88dB ⁽⁷⁾
2.2MHz ⁽⁸⁾	0.06dB ⁽⁸⁾	1.9dB ⁽⁸⁾	-88dB ⁽⁸⁾
Crosstalk (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
-42dB ⁽¹⁾	-22dB ⁽¹⁾	-5dB ⁽¹⁾	1.1mV ⁽¹⁾
-44dB ⁽²⁾	-22dB ⁽²⁾	-5dB ⁽²⁾	1.2mV ⁽²⁾
-45dB ⁽³⁾	-22dB ⁽³⁾	-5dB ⁽³⁾	1.2mV ⁽³⁾
-45dB ⁽⁴⁾	-22dB ⁽⁴⁾	-3dB ⁽⁴⁾	1.1mV ⁽⁴⁾
-41dB ⁽⁵⁾	-22dB ⁽⁵⁾	-3dB ⁽⁵⁾	1.2mV ⁽⁵⁾
-35dB ⁽⁶⁾	-22dB ⁽⁶⁾	2dB ⁽⁶⁾	1.2mV ⁽⁶⁾
-35dB ⁽⁷⁾	-22dB ⁽⁷⁾	8dB ⁽⁷⁾	1.2mV ⁽⁷⁾
-35dB ⁽⁸⁾	-22dB ⁽⁸⁾	13dB ⁽⁸⁾	1.2mV ⁽⁸⁾

Table 3. Measured performances of the Instrumentation Amplifier. Output voltage is 1V. ⁽¹⁾ Gain is set to 1V/V (0dB). ⁽²⁾ Gain is set to 2V/V (6dB). ⁽³⁾ Gain is set to 4V/V (12dB). ⁽⁴⁾ Gain is set to 5V/V (14dB). ⁽⁵⁾ Gain is set to 10V/V (20dB). ⁽⁶⁾ Gain is set to 20V/V (26dB). ⁽⁷⁾ Gain is set to 50V/V (34dB). ⁽⁸⁾ Gain is set to 100V/V (40dB).

Supplementary Materials 3: Transimpedance Amplifier

Fig. 1. Gain of transimpedance amplifier. Input resistor is set between 1kΩ and 100kΩ (top). Input current is set between 10μA and 200μA (bottom). TIA input is configured in single-ended mode.

Fig. 2. THD+N of transimpedance amplifier. Input resistor is set between 1kΩ and 100kΩ (top). Input current is set between 10μA and 200μA (bottom). TIA input is configured in single-ended mode.

Fig. 3. Gain of transimpedance amplifier. Input resistor is set between $1\text{k}\Omega$ and $100\text{k}\Omega$ (top). Input current is set between $10\mu\text{A}$ and $200\mu\text{A}$ (bottom). TIA input is configured in differential mode.

Fig. 4. THD+N of transimpedance amplifier. Input resistor is set between $1\text{k}\Omega$ and $100\text{k}\Omega$ (top). Input current is set between $10\mu\text{A}$ and $200\mu\text{A}$ (bottom). TIA input is configured in differential mode.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)
>10MHz ⁽¹⁾	40.0dB ⁽¹⁾	39.9dB ⁽¹⁾
3.0MHz ⁽²⁾	40.0dB ⁽²⁾	29.4dB ⁽²⁾
0.23MHz ⁽³⁾	40.0dB ⁽³⁾	10.2dB ⁽³⁾
THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
-43dB ⁽¹⁾	-23dB ⁽¹⁾	2.1mV ⁽¹⁾
-45dB ⁽²⁾	-34dB ⁽²⁾	1.9mV ⁽²⁾
-46dB ⁽³⁾	-37dB ⁽³⁾	2.0mV ⁽³⁾

Table 1. Measured performances of the TIA. Input current is 20 μ App. Input load is connected in a Single-Ended arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $R_L = 1k\Omega$. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 100k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)
3.0 MHz ⁽¹⁾	40.0dB ⁽¹⁾	29.4dB ⁽¹⁾
3.0 MHz ⁽²⁾	40.0dB ⁽²⁾	29.4dB ⁽²⁾
3.0 MHz ⁽³⁾	40.0dB ⁽³⁾	30.5dB ⁽³⁾
THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
-45dB ⁽¹⁾	-36dB ⁽¹⁾	2.0mV ⁽¹⁾
-55dB ⁽²⁾	-37dB ⁽²⁾	1.9mV ⁽²⁾
-67dB ⁽³⁾	-38dB ⁽³⁾	1.9mV ⁽³⁾

Table 2. Measured performances of the TIA. Input load is 10k Ω . Input load is connected in a Single-Ended arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $I_{in} = 5\mu$ App. ⁽²⁾ $I_{in} = 20\mu$ App. ⁽³⁾ $I_{in} = 200\mu$ App.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)
2.2MHz ⁽¹⁾	40.1dB ⁽¹⁾	25.9dB ⁽¹⁾
0.22MHz ⁽²⁾	40.0dB ⁽²⁾	7.0dB ⁽²⁾
0.022MHz ⁽³⁾	40.0dB ⁽³⁾	-1.2dB ⁽³⁾
THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
-48dB ⁽¹⁾	-39dB ⁽¹⁾	2.5mV ⁽¹⁾
-46dB ⁽²⁾	-35dB ⁽²⁾	2.9mV ⁽²⁾
-46dB ⁽³⁾	-25dB ⁽³⁾	3.1mV ⁽³⁾

Table 3. Measured performances of the TIA. Input current is 20 μ App. Input load is connected in a differential arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $R_L = 1k\Omega$. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 100k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)
0.22MHz ⁽¹⁾	40.0dB ⁽¹⁾	7dB ⁽¹⁾
0.22MHz ⁽²⁾	40.0dB ⁽²⁾	8.5dB ⁽²⁾
0.22MHz ⁽³⁾	40.0dB ⁽³⁾	18dB ⁽³⁾
THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
-45dB ⁽¹⁾	-28dB ⁽¹⁾	2.3mV ⁽¹⁾
-55dB ⁽²⁾	-30dB ⁽²⁾	2.6mV ⁽²⁾
-65dB ⁽³⁾	-25dB ⁽³⁾	3.0mV ⁽³⁾

Table 4. Measured performances of the TIA. Input load is 10k Ω . Input load is connected in a differential arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $I_{in} = 5\mu$ App. ⁽²⁾ $I_{in} = 20\mu$ App. ⁽³⁾ $I_{in} = 200\mu$ App.

Supplementary Materials 4: Voltage Driver

Fig 1. Measured Gain. Output voltage is 100mV. Output load is connected in a single-ended arrangement.

Fig 2. Measured output impedance. Output voltage is 100mV, 1V and 5V. Output load is connected in a single-ended arrangement.

Fig 3. Measured THD+N. Output voltage is 100mV, 1V and 5V. Output load is connected in a single-ended arrangement.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.9MHz ⁽¹⁾	0.80dB ⁽¹⁾	-6.4dB ⁽¹⁾	10Ω
7.9MHz ⁽²⁾	0.80dB ⁽²⁾	-6.4dB ⁽²⁾	
7.3MHz ⁽³⁾	-0.04dB ⁽³⁾	-8.4dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
26Ω	-49dB ⁽¹⁾	-19dB ⁽¹⁾	-30.1mV ⁽¹⁾
	-49dB ⁽²⁾	-19dB ⁽²⁾	-31.3mV ⁽²⁾
	-47dB ⁽³⁾	-16dB ⁽³⁾	-31.7mV ⁽³⁾

Table 1. Measured performances of the Voltage Driver. Output voltage is set to 100mVpp and is connected to the load is a single-ended configuration. ⁽¹⁾ Open load. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.5MHz ⁽¹⁾	0.80dB ⁽¹⁾	-6.4dB ⁽¹⁾	10Ω
7.5MHz ⁽²⁾	0.80dB ⁽²⁾	-6.4dB ⁽²⁾	
7.2MHz ⁽³⁾	-0.04dB ⁽³⁾	-8.4dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
26Ω	-63dB ⁽¹⁾	-28dB ⁽¹⁾	-33.4mV ⁽¹⁾
	-63dB ⁽²⁾	-28dB ⁽²⁾	-32.4mV ⁽²⁾
	-63dB ⁽³⁾	-30dB ⁽³⁾	-32.1mV ⁽³⁾

Table 2. Measured performances of the Voltage Driver. Output voltage is set to 1Vpp and is connected to the load is a single-ended configuration. ⁽¹⁾ Open load. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.3 MHz ⁽¹⁾	0.80dB ⁽¹⁾	-6.4dB ⁽¹⁾	10Ω
7.3 MHz ⁽²⁾	0.80dB ⁽²⁾	-6.4dB ⁽²⁾	
7.1 MHz ⁽³⁾	-0.05dB ⁽³⁾	-8.6dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
30Ω	-61 dB ⁽¹⁾	-7 dB ⁽¹⁾	-35.6mV ⁽¹⁾
	-61 dB ⁽²⁾	-7 dB ⁽²⁾	-34.4mV ⁽²⁾
	-60 dB ⁽³⁾	-9 dB ⁽³⁾	-33.6mV ⁽³⁾

Table 3. Measured performances of the Voltage Driver. Output voltage is set to 5Vpp and is connected to the load is a single-ended configuration. ⁽¹⁾ Open load. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Fig 4. Measured Gain. Output voltage is 100mV. Output load is connected in a differential arrangement.

Fig 5. Measured output impedance. Output voltage is 100mV, 1V and 5V. Output load is connected in a differential arrangement.

Fig 6. Measured THD+N. Output voltage is 100mV, 1V and 5V. Output load is connected in a differential arrangement.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.8 MHz ⁽¹⁾	6.8 dB ⁽¹⁾	2.2 dB ⁽¹⁾	20Ω
7.8 MHz ⁽²⁾	6.8 dB ⁽²⁾	2.2 dB ⁽²⁾	
7.2 MHz ⁽³⁾	5.2 dB ⁽³⁾	-2.0 dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
64Ω	-44 dB ⁽¹⁾	-17 dB ⁽¹⁾	-0.5mV ⁽¹⁾
	-46 dB ⁽²⁾	-17 dB ⁽²⁾	-0.3mV ⁽²⁾
	-45 dB ⁽³⁾	-13 dB ⁽³⁾	-0.8mV ⁽³⁾

Table 4. Measured performances of the Voltage Driver. Output voltage is set to 100mVpp and is connected to the load is a differential configuration. ⁽¹⁾ Open load. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.5 MHz ⁽¹⁾	6.8 dB ⁽¹⁾	1.9 dB ⁽¹⁾	20Ω
7.5 MHz ⁽²⁾	6.8 dB ⁽²⁾	1.9 dB ⁽²⁾	
7.1 MHz ⁽³⁾	5.2 dB ⁽³⁾	-2.1 dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
59Ω	-62 dB ⁽¹⁾	-31 dB ⁽¹⁾	-0.3mV ⁽¹⁾
	-62 dB ⁽²⁾	-31 dB ⁽²⁾	-0.2mV ⁽²⁾
	-63 dB ⁽³⁾	-28 dB ⁽³⁾	-0.4mV ⁽³⁾

Table 5. Measured performances of the Voltage Driver. Output voltage is set to 1Vpp and is connected to the load is a differential configuration. ⁽¹⁾ Open load. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.4 MHz ⁽¹⁾	6.8 dB ⁽¹⁾	1.4 dB ⁽¹⁾	20Ω
7.4 MHz ⁽²⁾	6.8 dB ⁽²⁾	1.4 dB ⁽²⁾	
7.0 MHz ⁽³⁾	5.2 dB ⁽³⁾	-2.2 dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
51Ω	-60 dB ⁽¹⁾	-17 dB ⁽¹⁾	-6.3mV ⁽¹⁾
	-60 dB ⁽²⁾	-17 dB ⁽²⁾	-6.2mV ⁽²⁾
	-62 dB ⁽³⁾	-14 dB ⁽³⁾	-7.4mV ⁽³⁾

Table 6. Measured performances of the Voltage Driver. Output voltage is set to 5Vpp and is connected to the load is a differential configuration. ⁽¹⁾ Open load. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$. ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Supplementary Materials 5: Current Driver

Fig 1. Measured Gain of the current driver. Output load is connected in a single-ended arrangement.

Fig 2. Measured output impedance of the current driver. Output load is connected in a differential arrangement.

Fig 3. Measured THD+N of the current driver. Output load is connected in a single-ended arrangement

Fig 4. Measured Gain of the current driver. Output load is connected in a single-ended arrangement. Gain is set to high-mode gain.

Fig 5. Measured output impedance of the current driver. Output load is connected in a single-ended arrangement. Gain is set to high-mode gain.

Fig 6. Measured gain of the current driver. Output load is connected in a differential arrangement.

Fig 6. Measured output impedance of the current driver. Output load is connected in a differential arrangement.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
>10MHz ⁽¹⁾	-89.7dB ⁽¹⁾	-90.9dB ⁽¹⁾	> 1MΩ
2MHz ⁽²⁾	-89.7dB ⁽²⁾	-104.3dB ⁽²⁾	
0.21MHz ⁽³⁾	-89.8dB ⁽³⁾	-120.0dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
2.72kΩ	-23dB ⁽¹⁾	-8dB ⁽¹⁾	0.21μA ⁽¹⁾
	-41dB ⁽²⁾	-10dB ⁽²⁾	0.23μA ⁽²⁾
	-41dB ⁽³⁾	2dB ⁽³⁾	0.22μA ⁽³⁾

Table 1. Measured performances of the Current Driver. Output current is set to 20uApp. Gain is set to low mode and load is connected in single-ended arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$ ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 1k\Omega$. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.5MHz ⁽¹⁾	-81.1dB ⁽¹⁾	-86.5dB ⁽¹⁾	> 1MΩ
1.8MHz ⁽²⁾	-81.1dB ⁽²⁾	-100.8dB ⁽²⁾	
0.18MHz ⁽³⁾	-81.2dB ⁽³⁾	-116.0dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
2.66kΩ	-40dB ⁽¹⁾	-21dB ⁽¹⁾	0.55μA ⁽¹⁾
	-55dB ⁽²⁾	-20dB ⁽²⁾	0.61μA ⁽²⁾
	-55dB ⁽³⁾	-9dB ⁽³⁾	0.72μA ⁽³⁾

Table 2. Measured performances of the Current Driver. Output current is set to 100uApp. Gain is set to high mode and load is connected in single-ended arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$ ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 1k\Omega$. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
7.5MHz ⁽¹⁾	-81.1dB ⁽¹⁾	-86.5dB ⁽¹⁾	> 1MΩ
1.8MHz ⁽²⁾	-81.1dB ⁽²⁾	-100.8dB ⁽²⁾	
0.18MHz ⁽³⁾	-81.2dB ⁽³⁾	-116.0dB ⁽³⁾	
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
2.66kΩ	-40dB ⁽¹⁾	-21dB ⁽¹⁾	0.55μA ⁽¹⁾
	-55dB ⁽²⁾	-20dB ⁽²⁾	0.61μA ⁽²⁾
	-55dB ⁽³⁾	-9dB ⁽³⁾	0.72μA ⁽³⁾

Table 3. Measured performances of the Current Driver. Output current is set to 20uApp. Gain is set to low mode and load is connected in differential arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $R_L = 100\Omega$ ⁽³⁾ $R_L = 1k\Omega$. ⁽²⁾ $R_L = 10k\Omega$.

Bandwidth	Gain (1kHz)	Gain (10MHz)	Output Impedance (1kHz)
2.2MHz ⁽¹⁾	-89.7dB ⁽¹⁾	-104dB ⁽¹⁾	> 1M Ω ⁽¹⁾
2.2MHz ⁽²⁾	-89.7dB ⁽²⁾	-105dB ⁽²⁾	> 1M Ω ⁽²⁾
2.2MHz ⁽³⁾	-89.7dB ⁽³⁾	-105dB ⁽³⁾	> 1M Ω ⁽³⁾
Output Impedance (10MHz)	THD+N (1kHz)	THD+N (10MHz)	DC Offset
2.72k Ω ⁽¹⁾	-40dB ⁽¹⁾	-21dB ⁽¹⁾	0.55 μ A ⁽¹⁾
2.82k Ω ⁽²⁾	-55dB ⁽²⁾	-20dB ⁽²⁾	0.61 μ A ⁽²⁾
2.41k Ω ⁽³⁾	-55dB ⁽³⁾	-9dB ⁽³⁾	0.72 μ A ⁽³⁾

Table 4. Measured performances of the Current Driver. Output load is 1k Ω . Gain is set to low mode and load is connected in single-ended arrangement. ⁽¹⁾ $I_{out} = 1\mu$ App. ⁽²⁾ $I_{out} = 10\mu$ App. ⁽³⁾ $I_{out} = 50\mu$ App.